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Healthy Life Expectancy in Europe

Between 2010 and 2020 it grew 1.4 years on average for the countries analyzed

The Eurostat calculates the health expectation in Europe. The data are collected through interviews. The indicator also considers the possibility of living a life in health without disabilities. The indicator is also known as life expectancy without disabilities in Europe. In the analysis, only countries with a complete historical series were considered.

Ranking of countries by value of life expectancy in Europe. Malta is in the first place for the value of the health life expectancy in Europe with an amount of 70.50 years, followed by Norway with an amount of 68.60 years, and from Spain with an amount of 66.30 years. In the middle of the standings there are Hungary with an amount of 62.50 years, followed by Poland with an amount of 62.30 years and by the Czech Republic with an amount of 61.60 years. Lithuania closes the ranking with an amount of 56.80 years, Slovakia with a value of 56.70 years and Latvia with a value of 53.40 years. On average in the countries considered the value of health life expectancy is 62.18 years.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of the health expectation of life in Europe between 2010 and 2020. Slovenia is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the health life expectancy with a value of 20,78% equal to an amount of 11.2 years, followed by Germany with a growth of 12.69% equal to 7.4 years, and from Hungary with an amount of 8.7% equal to an amount of 5 years. In the middle of the standings there are the Netherlands with an amount of 0.66% equal to an amount of 0.4 years, followed by Malta with a value of -0.28% equal to an amount of -0.2 units and from Ireland with an amount of -0.3% equal to an amount of -0.2 years. Switzerland closes the ranking with an amount of -4.65% equal to an amount of -3 years, followed by Lithuania with a value of -5.02% equal to an amount of -3 years and by Denmark with a value of -6.45% equal to an amount of -4 years. On average for the countries analyzed, the value of the health expectation of life has grown by 1.4% equal to an amount of 0.75 years.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is proposed a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Two different Clusters have been identified or:

- Cluster 1: Ireland, Greece, Spain, Bulgaria, Norway, Malta, Cyprus, Belgium, France, Czech Republic, Luxembourg;
- Cluster 2: Lithuania, Estonia, Austria, Romania, Croatia, Slovenia, Slovakia, Latvia, Portugal, Hungary, Netherlands, Denmark, Poland, Switzerland, Germany.

From the point of view of couponing, the following system of the Clusters or: C1 > C2 is the following system. From a geographical point of view, it appears that the countries of central-northern Europe and Eastern Europe have a lower value of health life expectancy. From a quantitative point of view, considering the median of the Clusters, it is possible to verify that the countries of the Cluster 2 have a value of the health life expectancy of about 6 years less than the value of the Cluster 1.

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Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below through the application of the Euclidean distance. Four network structures are identified, three of which simplified and one complex. The complex network structure consists of the following elements or:

- The Czech Republic has a connection with France for an amount of 0.5 units, with Belgium for an amount of 0.46 units;
- France has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.5 units and with Belgium for an amount of 0.46 units;
- Belgium has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.46 units and with France for an amount of 0.38 units.

There are also the following structures with complex networks or:

- Netherlands and Denmark have a connection equal to an amount of 0.47 units;
- Greece and Bulgaria have a connection for a value of 0.57 units;
- Austria and Croatia have a connection for an amount of 0.55 units.

Conclusions. The value of life expectancy in good greeting in Europe has grown on average for the countries considered to be an amount equal to a value of 1.4 years. However, it is necessary to consider that there are countries that have significantly increased the value of life expectancy in Europe such as Slovenia, Germany and Hungary. In general, all European countries have experienced a growth in life expectancy in convergence with the levels of the countries of Western Europe. It should be considered that the data do not take into consideration the effects of the Covid 19 pandemic. There is still a significant divergence between Eastern Europe and Europe. It follows that also in the light of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict, the will of the Eastern countries to associate with Europe is understandable, to have better living conditions and not only from an economic point of view, but also from the point of view of 'life expectation. In the data sample analyzed some countries such as Italy are missing. It therefore follows that the analysis is partial. It is likely that the set of Covid-19, Climate Change, Russian-Ukraine crisis, growth of the price of energy, and inflation, can create the conditions for a worsening of the health life expectancy by limiting the possibility of the population to have access to care, to adequate sources of heating and energy, and compressing the real income.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

C1>C2

